

A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND STRESS OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract:

The present study aimed to study the influence of emotional intelligence on stress of elementary school teachers. This study adopted survey method of research. Participants were 260 elementary school teachers randomly selected from various schools in Bangalore. It is to determine the sources of emotional intelligence and stress for classroom teacher and teachers working in elementary schools and methods that are used by them in order to emotional intelligence with the stress. In this research, qualitative and quantitative methods have been used jointly. The data collection tool for quantitative research is emotional intelligence scale constructed and standardized by Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Detha and Upinder Dhar (2001), Vedant Publications, Lucknow and Stress Questionnaire constructed by Latha Satish (1997). The analysis has been done through SPSS 23 for Windows; mean, standard deviation; t-ratio and F-ratio were calculated. The study also revealed that there was no significant difference in emotional intelligence and stress with respect to gender, locality of institution, mode of management, years of teaching experience, marital status and type of family towards elementary school teachers.

Key Words: Elementary School Teacher, Emotional Intelligence, Stress.

Introduction:

Teaching is a noble profession. The teachers are the heart and core of the whole educational process. The strength of the education system largely depends upon the quality of teachers. These individuals should be able to impart character among the pupils. They are expected to arouse enthusiasm and be a source of inspiration for the real pupils. No doubt, the teachers are the real architects of a nation and the makers of the humanity.

Origin of the Concept of Emotional Intelligence:

The origins of the concept of emotional intelligence dates to Darwin's work on the importance of emotional expression to survival and successful adaptation. In the 1900s even though traditional definitions of intelligence emphasized cognitive aspects such as memory and problem solving, several influential researchers in the intelligence field of study had begun to recognize the importance of non-cognitive aspects. For instance as early as 1920, R. K. Thorndike used the term social intelligence to describe the skill of understanding and managing other people (Hein, 2005).

Way to Develop the Emotional Intelligence in an Educational Institute:

The administrators, the teachers and students are obliged to take the responsibility together in developing the emotional intelligence at a personal level, at the group level and at the organizational level at the same time. The teacher's duty in developing the emotional intelligence is that he/she enable students to use vocabularies pertaining to the emotion and teach students to comport appropriately. The emotional intelligence training is a scrupulous and difficult task. The test commencement in this task is for the teachers to understand their own emotion, feelings and personality; the teachers should keep in mind of the motto 'Preach who teach you.' Teachers should be careful of their own words and emotion.

Stress and Sources of Stress for Teachers:

The stress, which has become a societal problem today, has become almost a part of our daily lives Sabuncuoğlu, Z. and Melek Tüz. (2003). Stress is a phenomenon that has an impact on people and affecting their behaviors, their job performances and communication with their co-workers. Selye defines stress as an undetermined reaction demonstrated by physique against pressure Aksoy, A. and Kutluca, F. (2005). According to Allen (1983), the stress, regardless of giving or not giving pleasure or pain, signifies a non-special reaction of the body toward any request implied on it for its adaptation Baştuğ, A. (2009). With a general definition, stress is a physiological and psychological reaction of an individual toward him/herself and external environment as a result of being affected by involved environment and working conditions. Stress does not occur automatically. It is developed by the effect of the transformations occurred in individuals' environment Eren, E. (2008). Due to several reasons such as educational policies that are constantly changing in our country, difficulties in the implication, deficiencies in physical conditions, in adequacy of the conditions that teachers are experiencing, teachers proceed to working under intense stress. Especially, it is seen that different factors are included in stress resources of teachers working in elementary schools. According to Turna (2014), different sources of stress

affecting the teacher are; demotivated students, time pressure, workload, disciplinary environment, coping with novelty, being evaluated by others, problems with co-workers, status, administrative reasons, conflict of duties and in appropriate working conditions.

Statement of the Problem:

The present study is entitled “A study on emotional intelligence and stress of elementary school teachers.

Research Method:

In the present study the investigator employed the survey methods.

Sampling of the Study:

Regarding the sample of teachers, on an average thirteen (13) elementary school teacher participants were selected randomly from each of the 20 selected elementary schools. On the whole, the tools were administered to 260 elementary schools teachers. Despite careful supervision, it was found that 2 tools were answered partially and which were perfectly alright could be considered for the analysis.

Objectives of the Study:

To study the significant difference of the following variables on the emotional intelligence of the elementary school teachers

- Gender : Male / Female
- Locality of Institution : Rural / Urban
- Mode of Management : Government / Private / Aided
- Year of Teaching Experience : Below 10 / Above 10
- Marital Status : Married / Unmarried
- Type of family : Nuclear / Joint

To study the significant difference of the following variables on the stress of the elementary school teachers

- Gender : Male / Female
- Locality of Institution : Rural / Urban
- Mode of Management : Government / Private / Aided
- Year of Teaching Experience : Below 10 / Above 10
- Marital Status : Married / Unmarried
- Type of family : Nuclear / Joint

Hypotheses of the Study:

There is a significant difference in the Emotional intelligence elementary school teachers in relation to the following variables.

- Gender : Male / Female
- Locality of Institution : Rural / Urban
- Mode of Management : Government / Private / Aided
- Years of Teaching Experience : Below 10 / Above 10
- Marital Status : Married / Unmarried
- Type of family : Nuclear / Joint

There is a significant difference in the stress elementary school teachers in relation to the following variables.

- Gender : Male / Female
- Locality of Institution : Rural / Urban
- Mode of Management : Government / Private / Aided
- Years of Teaching Experience : Below 10 / Above 10
- Marital Status : Married / Unmarried
- Type of family : Nuclear / Joint

Tools Used in the Present Study:

- Emotional Intelligence Scale Constructed and Standardized by Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Deth and Upinder Dhar (2001), Vedant Publications, Lucknow.
- Stress Questionnaire constructed by Latha Satish (1997)

Analysis of Data and Interpretation:

Table 1: Showing t- ratio of emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their gender

Group	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Male	133	94.54	34.93	0.694	Not Significant
Female	127	91.54	34.86		

Table 1 indicates that calculated t-ratio (0.694) is not significant at 0.05 (1.96) level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of

elementary school teachers in relation to their gender. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their gender is rejected.

Table 2: Showing t- ratio of emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their locality of institution

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Rural	113	92.48	35.15	0.24	Not Significant
Urban	147	93.53	34.75		

Table 2 indicates that calculated t-ratio (0.240) is not significant at 0.05(1.96) level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their locality of institution. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their locality of institution is rejected.

Table 3: Showing F- ratio of emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their mode of management

Mode of Management	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	'F' Value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Between Groups	4136.108	2	2068.054	1.710	Not Significant
Within Groups	310757.196	257	1209.172		
Total	314893.304	259			

Table 3 indicates that calculated F-ratio (1.710) is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their mode of management. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their mode of management is rejected.

Table 4: Showing t- ratio of emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their years of teaching experience

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Below 10 years	114	91.52	36.75	0.634	Not Significant
Above 10 years	146	94.29	33.40		

Table 4 indicates that calculated t-ratio (0.634) is not significant at 0.05(1.96) level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their years of teaching experience. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their years of teaching experience is rejected.

Table 5: Showing t- ratio of emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their marital status

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Married	124	95.27	34.73	0.968	Not Significant
Unmarried	136	91.08	35.00		

Table 5 indicates that calculated t-ratio (0.968) is not significant at 0.05(1.96) level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their marital status. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their marital status is rejected.

Table 6: Showing t- ratio of emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their type of family

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Nuclear	122	90.20	35.08	1.252	Not Significant
Joint	138	95.62	34.60		

Table 6 indicates that calculated t-ratio (1.252) is not significant at 0.05(1.96) level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their type of family. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their type of family is rejected.

Table 7: Showing t- ratio of stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their gender

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Male	133	32.53	7.32	0.118	Not Significant
Female	127	32.63	6.88		

Table 7 indicates that calculated t-ratio (0.118) is not significant at 0.05(1.96) level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in stress of elementary

school teachers in relation to their gender. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their gender is rejected.

Table 8: Showing t- ratio of stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their locality of institution

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Rural	113	32.25	6.86	0.652	Not Significant
Urban	147	32.83	7.28		

Table 8 indicates that calculated t-ratio (0.652) is not significant at 0.05(1.96) level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their locality of institution. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their locality of institution is rejected.

Table 9: Showing F- ratio of stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their mode of management

Mode of Management	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	'F' Value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Between Groups	254.056	2	127.028	2.550	Not Significant
Within Groups	12803.082	257	49.817		
Total	13057.138	259			

Table 9 indicates that calculated F-ratio (2.550) is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their mode of management. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their mode of management is rejected.

Table 10: Showing t- ratio of stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their years of teaching experience

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Below 10 years	114	33.09	6.98	1.027	Not Significant
Above 10 years	146	32.18	7.19		

Table 10 indicates that calculated t-ratio (1.027) is not significant at 0.05(1.96) level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their years of teaching experience. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their years of teaching experience is rejected.

Table 11: Showing t- ratio of stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their marital status

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Married	124	32.85	7.52	0.585	Not Significant
Unmarried	136	32.33	6.70		

Table 11 indicates that calculated t-ratio (0.585) is not significant at 0.05(1.96) level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their marital status. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their marital status is rejected.

Table 12: Showing t- ratio of stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their type of family

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Level of Significance at 0.05
Nuclear	122	32.16	7.38	0.898	Not Significant
Joint	138	32.95	6.84		

Table 12 indicates that calculated t-ratio (0.898) is not significant at 0.05(1.96) level of significance. Therefore, from the table it may be concluded that there is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their type of family. Hence, framed hypothesis that there is significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their type of family is rejected.

Major Findings of the Study:

- There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their gender.
- There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their locality of institution.
- There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their mode of management.
- There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their years of teaching experience.
- There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their marital status.
- There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of elementary school teachers in relation to their type of family.

- There is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their gender.
- There is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their locality of institution.
- There is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their mode of management.
- There is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their years of teaching experience.
- There is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their marital status.
- There is no significant difference in stress of elementary school teachers in relation to their type of family.

Educational Implications:

- To strengthen the emotional intelligence aspects of the elementary school teachers, guidance and counselling services are to be made an integral part of the school management.
- As teachers under different managements differ in dimensions and emotional intelligence, in-depth studies help to identify the effective factors from each type of management and for their dissemination to other organizations.
- Emotional intelligence and stress factors are to be considered in teacher training programmes and in in-service training programmes.

Conclusion:

Emotions and emotional intelligence have been duly recognized to have particular relevance to school teachers who are vulnerable to high levels of stress and burnout due to the nature of their work; indeed, teaching is one of the most stressful jobs whose success is fundamentally based on the effective interaction between students and teachers. However, teaching is becoming a very challenging job that requires teachers to have adaptive abilities such as appraisal of self and others, regulation of self and others, and effective utilization of emotions. Many studies have been conducted on emotional intelligence and its relationship with various demographic variables which have been shown to be complex and multifaceted. According to findings obtained from qualitative research, issues which teachers have gone through stress most are originating from school administration, teaching profession and school facilities. According to participants' opinions, sources of stress affecting teachers originating from school facilities; lack of resources and technological facilities, lack of space, long working hours, big-small size of the school building, transformational difficulties, heating conditions of school building and eating problems. It is though provoking that even though teachers are working in schools. Besides not having economically satisfactory remuneration, teachers demonstrate great effort regardless of many difficulties of the profession. In exchange of all these efforts, while promotion opportunities are limited teachers had been forced to keep up with constantly changing educational system. All of those are factors for teachers to experience stress. As good teachers do their work at the highest level in schools with good leadership, a school principal who is both mentally and physically unwell could have a potentially dreadful effect on the well-being of both teachers and students. In this point of view, high teacher trust in principals' support will help teachers to cope with stress and, in turn, students' rights to success are adequately addressed.

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